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Published Journal Papers - 2016

(Total Number 177 by 26 Faculty Members)

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.261032>

1. Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T. & Suresh Kumar, P.M. (2016). [ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education](#). *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 11-24, (January 2016), ISSN: 2249-0558, I.F. 6. 269.
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